

**Via Weber Ferguson Approach
 Subtotal Maxillectomy Performed**

Patient admitted to Anand Hospital with a diagnosis of Mucormycosis of left maxilla, extending to left infra temporal region, involving the buccal pad of fat area, so operated for left partial Maxillectomy via Weber Ferguson Approach by Senior Maxillofacial Surgeon **Dr Puneet Kalra**, Left Maxillary Sinus was debrided by Senior ENT Surgeon **Dr. Puneet Bhargava**, procedure was performed under General Anaesthesia under the supervision of Senior Anesthesiologist **Dr Sanjay Agarwal** and following this Patient received Amphotericin treatment for 21 days, and discharged uneventfully.

Post maxillectomy rehabilitation was performed after 8 months, via Zygomatic and Cortico-basal Implants under the supervision of Senior Implantologist **Dr Rahul Vaid & Dr Puneet Kalra**

Dr. Puneet Kalra
 Consultant Maxillofacial Surgeon
 Anand Hospital, Meerut

Dr. Puneet Bhargava
 Senior Consultant ENT Surgeon
 Anand Hospital, Meerut

Via Weber Ferguson Approach, Subtotal Maxillectomy Performed

Immediate Post -Op Picture

**Via Cortico Basal Implants,
 Fixed Prosthesis Fabricated**

**Maxillectomy Defect Can Be
 Appreciated On Left Side**

Dr. Sanjay Agarwal
 Senior Anesthesiologist
 Anand Hospital, Meerut

Dr. Rahul Vaid
 Teacher of Corticobasal Implants
 Meerut

6 Month Post Dental Rehabilitation